

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

METHODS AND TECHNIQUES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF COGNITIVE ACTIVITY IN MIDDLE-LEVEL SCHOOLCHILDREN

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Abstract

In the conditions of modern society, the role of a foreign language is very large, since a foreign language is not only a means of intercultural communication, but also provides the mastery of the skills and abilities of students' cognitive and self-educational activities. One of the main factors of successful mastery of a foreign language is personal interest, the personal desire of each student to master a foreign language. That is, it is motivation that plays a key role, encouraging each student to active cognitive activity. But, unfortunately, often teachers are faced with the unwillingness of students to do anything: difficult texts, large amounts of information and other similar reasons deprive our students of the most important thing - the desire to learn. Therefore, the primary task of the teacher is the formation of cognitive interest in teaching a foreign language. What can motivate a student? I will consider those techniques that I use myself in my work and which, in my opinion, effectively motivate students to active cognitive activity in the classroom.

Keywords: cognitive activity, foreign language teaching, motivation, formation of cognitive interest.

Introduction

Many of the above methods and techniques work just as well with the middle class as they do with the elementary grades. But here the spirit of rivalry is already much more pronounced, which can be used to increase interest in the subject. To do this, it is good to develop your own system of bonuses with which you can encourage the guys. And this system can work equally well both when performing tasks individually and in pairs or groups. For example, those guys who do the tasks faster and more correctly than anyone else can get an extra point to their final mark for the lesson. Or if the teacher evaluates the results of work at each stage of the lesson, then this score can be added to the mark that the guys receive at the end of one or another stage of the lesson, which, in turn, has a positive effect on the final mark for the lesson, which is the arithmetic average of marks for all stages of the lesson.

Materials and types of research

The main tasks of my activity are:

- unity of education and upbringing;
- creation of favorable psychological and pedagogical conditions for the education, upbringing and development of the child's personality.

I believe that an important factor in learning, as a means of educating a personality, is the organization of the learning process. Therefore, it is necessary to influence the child's feelings, his need-motivational sphere in order to cause a desire for self-education of certain qualities and personality traits. [1]

1. Creating an atmosphere in the classroom in which they feel the need for training sessions, perceive new knowledge with interest.

Goals:

- inclusion in the educational process at will;

- creation of a psychologically comfortable state of students in the classroom, which increases the effectiveness of classes, helps the children understand the educational material being studied and helps them not to experience difficulties in studying special subjects.

1) To learn how to solve problematic problems, I use the following method. First, using an example of a fairly simple task, the steps that need to be taken to solve it are described in detail, step by step. Each action is decomposed into operations performed in a certain sequence. For actions and operations, examples and possible options for their implementation are shown. As a result, a generalized scheme for applying the method for solving a certain type of problem is created. Then the students are offered a similar task, which the students solve on their own, answering the questions given in the text. Questions are compiled in accordance with the method application scheme and require the student not only to perform actions and operations, but also to justify the need for their implementation. Solving the following training tasks, students learn to perform actions in changed and gradually becoming more complex conditions. At the same time, they still answer a number of sequentially posed questions. [3]

The first training tasks correspond to the mandatory level of training, the subsequent tasks are considered more complex. The student can choose the level of difficulty of the tasks independently.

2) The use of video materials, which are an effective teaching tool. I use a small video recording as an epigraph of the lesson, which provides positive emotional motivation for learning new material. The use of video films in explaining or reinforcing new material is effective only if it is actively perceived by students. To do this, in the process of showing the video film, if necessary, give clarifications and clarifications, repeating the fragment, asking clarifying questions. [2]

3) The following texts contribute to the formation of an open cognitive position:

- giving students the opportunity to realize the existence of several approaches to the same situation and work within the framework of different approaches;
- suggesting several options for solving the same problem;
- containing conflicting data;
- developing the ability to perceive unexpected information;
- suggesting the appearance of errors and their discussion;
- giving the opportunity to see the perspective in the study of the subject and refer to the already studied material from a new point of view, etc. [9]

4) When selecting educational material, I take into account the various intellectual inclinations of students. I pay special attention to the actualization of the children's intuitive experience: the expression of doubts, beliefs, "outstripping" ideas, emotional assessments of educational material are encouraged.

5) Formation of the ability to admire, doubt, be surprised. This is done in different ways. One of them is a demonstration experiment. It is surprise that makes one independently seek the truth, gives rise to a desire to verify the correctness of one's assumptions. Only a person who knows how to doubt and wonder can think actively and creatively.

6) The development of the creative abilities of students, taking into account their individuality, the education of their independence and initiative is facilitated by laboratory and practical work.

7) An important aspect of the development of students' creative abilities is the solution of experimental problems. I try to bring the content of experimental tasks as close as possible to real situations. [8]

2. Creative tasks.

Goals:

- increase students' interest in the subject;
- give students the opportunity to express their creativity;
- develop students' speech, the ability to defend their own opinion.

To strengthen knowledge, develop interest in the subject and the relationship with other subjects, students are offered creative tasks that can be expressed:

1. in compiling a crossword puzzle on a topic, using it to control the knowledge of other students;
2. in the picture;
3. in the preparation of reference diagrams and notes.

At the beginning of each subsequent lesson, there is a defense, discussion and evaluation of the creative task, both by the author of the work and by the comrades in the group.

Efficiency

Creative tasks provide an opportunity to express themselves to any of the students, while the student chooses the forms of work for himself. So, children with more often work with diagrams or tables. [4]

3. Didactic games.

Goals:

- increase interest in the subject;

- individualize and collectivize the cognitive activity of students in the classroom;

- development of observation, the ability to see the unusual in familiar things;

- to activate the cognitive activity of students. [7]

Play, learning and labor are the main human activities. At the same time, the game prepares the student, both for learning and for work, itself, being both learning and work.

1) Games with strict rules:

- work with ciphers (chainwords; braids; rebuses; puzzles).

2) Role play:

- dramatization games;
- auctions;
- competitions.

3) Correctional games:

- psychological games-exercises;
- logical games;
- station games;
- travel games.

4) Game-seminar.

The best form of its implementation is a game like the television "What, where, when?". The number of questions can include on the topic covered, applied on practical application and interdisciplinary. Seminars can also be held in the style of other games: "Hour of Stars", "Field of Miracles", etc. [10]

5) Press conferences.

Efficiency

Practice shows that lessons based on the game method significantly increase students' interest in the subject, allow them to better memorize formulations, definitions, formulas, and, most importantly, "liberate" the student, his thinking. The assimilation of educational material is facilitated, each student is included in the work in the lesson, control of each task is possible, the level of motivation during training has increased, and feedback from students has improved. [8]

4. Use of information technologies.

Goals:

- improvement of the educational process through the use of information and communication technologies;
- formation of skills for working with information and educational resources.

A special place in the conditions of global informatization is occupied by information technologies, which we consider as:

- a learning tool that ensures the effectiveness of the educational process;
- a tool of knowledge that contributes to the formation of a natural-scientific worldview;
- a means of developing a personality capable of adapting to new achievements of scientific and technological progress;
- an object of study that broadens one's horizons and opens up new opportunities for improving educational and cognitive activity;
- a means of communication that ensures the optimization of the solution of educational problems. [6]

Efficiency

The practice of using information technology has confirmed the theoretical assumptions that IT contributes to:

- development of analytical abilities (analysis of information models, comparison, generalization);
- development of projection and design abilities;
- the development of mental functions (logical thinking, memory, attention, imagination, perception, etc.);
- the formation of communication skills;
- development of the ability to build information models of the processes under study;
- developing the ability to foresee the consequences of decisions and draw the right conclusions;
- identifying the adequacy and applicability of the method to the condition of the problem;
- readiness for independent work. [5]

Research results

In this paper, those means of activating the cognitive activity of students are proposed, which I successfully apply in my lessons. For example, I use such methods for 9 classes.

The "Brownian motion" technique involves the movement of students around the class in order to collect information on the proposed topic, while simultaneously practicing the studied grammatical constructions. Each participant receives a sheet with a list of questions and tasks. The teacher helps to formulate questions and answers and ensures that the interaction is conducted in English.

The method of "brainstorming" is an operational method of solving a problem based on stimulating creative activity. The participants of the discussion are invited to express as many possible solutions as possible, from the total number of ideas expressed, the most successful ones are selected that can be used in practice.

The options for using this method in a foreign language lesson can be the following:

1. Start the lesson with a brainstorming session as a speech charge –

WarmingUp, asking students questions: What are your associations with ...?

What do you associate with ...? What immediately comes into your mind when you hear ...?

2. Invite students to relax, tune in to the topic of reflection, take pens and write down the thoughts that come to their mind on a particular topic / problem.

3. Brainstorming as an interactive method of organizing a group discussion at the pre-text stage. The use of this technique involves step-by-step implementation.

Step 1 - warm-up (lasts 3 minutes). Over the course of several lessons, the topic is studied. The teacher suggests brainstorming with the participation of all the students of the group and name as many ideas as possible that they associate with this topic. A mental map (cluster) is being compiled.

Step 2 – combining students into mini-groups.

Step 3 – Work in mini-groups for 7 minutes. The teacher clearly states the problem or question that needs to be solved. So, for example, you can suggest brainstorming in mini-groups on the problem of the text to be read by students. The task of students is to express

and write down as many ideas as possible (even the most absurd), and then after reading the text to draw a conclusion.

The "Illustration" method: The teacher downloads the movie in advance. After watching the film and discussing, the participants formulate the topic of the lesson and its goals.

The method of "Associations" allows you to use imaginative thinking, memory. The first student receives a card from the teacher and names the associations that he has with this word. The card is passed along the chain until it returns to the teacher. Each student has the opportunity to express their thoughts at a fast pace.

The "Pathfinders" method is aimed at teaching children to work with various sources of information. The teacher puts up a poster or writes a lesson topic on the blackboard. For example, "Faces of London" ("Sights of London"). Next, students are asked to recall the main objects that are related to this topic: museums and art galleries, historical buildings, royal palaces, cathedrals, parks, etc. and write them down on the blackboard. Next, we proceed to the elaboration of the content of the topic.

The "Braggart" method is used to train grammatical skills in oral speech. It is necessary to prepare cards with the names of the temporary forms of the English language, an option without auxiliary means is also possible. The "braggart" draws out the time in which he has to come up with a proposal. The rest should refute his statement (make a negative sentence) or express surprise (ask a general question). If the "braggart" is wrong, the one who corrected him becomes a "braggart".

The "Traffic light" method is used to work with grammar. Students pick up red and green cards, choosing the correct grammatical forms.

In conclusion, it should be noted that all active methods and techniques develop communication skills, help establish emotional contacts between students, teach them to work in a team, listen to the opinions of their comrades, establish closer contact between students and the teacher.

Conclusion

One of the main tasks of a teacher is to organize learning activities in such a way that students develop needs for creative transformation of educational material in order to acquire new knowledge. To work on the activation of cognitive activity means to form a positive attitude of students to learning activities, to develop their desire for a deeper knowledge of the subjects being studied. The main task of the teacher is to increase the proportion of internal motivation for learning in the structure of students' motivation.

High cognitive activity is possible only in an interesting lesson, when the student is interested in the subject of study.

Any teacher, awakening interest in his subject, not only transfers experience, but also strengthens self-confidence, regardless of the student's abilities. It is necessary to develop creative abilities in weak students, not to let the more capable ones stop in their development,

to teach everyone to cultivate willpower, strong character and determination in solving complex tasks. All this is the education of a creative person in the broadest and deepest sense of the word. But in order to create a deep interest of students in the subject, to develop their cognitive activity, it is necessary to search for additional means that stimulate the development of general activity, independence, personal initiative and creativity.

Ultimately, the quality of the presentation of the material and the effectiveness of its assimilation significantly increases, and, consequently, the motivation for learning a foreign language on the part of schoolchildren.

Such different methods develop creativity, the ability to focus on specific tasks, interact in a group, analyze your own and other people's ideas.

Thus, the use of active teaching methods in the classroom provides a high level of interest of students, their cognitive and creative activity, allows you to create a situation of success for each student. This, in turn, helps to make the learning process rich, high-quality, effective and psychologically comfortable not only for students, but also for teachers.

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